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FROM REAL TO VIRTUAL PETS

THE EVOLUTION OF ARTIFICIAL COMPANIONS AS PET

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ABSTRACT

Real pets function as companions in human life and most owners believe that pets are family members or friends. However, real pets have problems of cleaning, care, nurturing space constraints, and other issues while the artificial companion, which has real pet function and can be substituted for real pets. The purpose of the study is to find out the design direction, understand the technical and functional changes of artificial companions, as well as the needs of users. The study analyzes the evolution of artificial companions from relevant literature, STS studies, and Need-hierarchy theory, and then infers the developmental trends to help designers develop new products. Finally, the evolution process is divided into five phases: Real interaction→ Imagine driving→ Mimicry of reality→ Multiple activity→ Intellectual interaction. The study also concludes that the developmental trends of artificial companions point towards the online virtual pet, and the online virtual pet will emphasize the self-expression and the social interaction on the Internet.

Keywords: artificial companion, real pet, virtual pet

INTRODUCTION

In the U.S., *pet expenditures have doubled over the past ten years* (Mosteller, 2008) and *most pet owners consider pets as members of their families and even contribute to sense of self* (Belk, 1988; Brown, 2004; Sanders, 1990; Cavanaugh, Leonard, & Scammon, 2008). This condition reflects the importance of pets in human life.

Taking care of a real pet can be inconvenient as they have problems of cleaning, caring, and nurturing space constraints (Kanoh, 2008). *The Statistics Bureau of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications in Japan surveyed "Time Use and Leisure Activities in 2006,"* and found that people

who live in collective housing find it easier to own a virtual pet than a real pet (Kanoh, 2008).

In fact, artificial companions have become widely embraced in digital entertainment (Kusahara, 2001; Wilks, 2006) and because the pet robots have some of the functions of real pets, such as company or comfort, they can be substituted for real pets. The first successful product was the Tamagotchi, children and adults spent most of their leisure time to interact with the Tamagotchi at that time around the world (Kusahara, 2001). *The extraordinary thing about the Tamagotchi (and the Furby) phenomenon was that people who knew better began to feel guilt about their behavior towards a small cheap and simple toy that could not even speak* (Wilks, 2006). Benyon and Mival (2008) also pointed out that *artificial companions can lead to enhanced emotional status and evoke an emotional investment.*

The successful of artificial companions is not due to the realism of the artificial pets, such as the Tamagotchi and its successor were merely crude animated figures presented on low-tech displays and the AIBO, being designed as a robot with no fur (Kaplan, 2001). Wilks (2006) also mentioned that *the notion of artificial companions as a socially important paradigm for language and speech research in the next ten years. Over the next decade, it is likely that robotic pets will become not only more computationally sophisticated and capable of action, but also more available for use* (Aylett, 2002; Yokoyama, Ribb, & Turner, 2004).

The study analyzes the evolution process of artificial companions can know the sequence of development ideas clearly and understand the correlation between technology and users' demands. The evolution of artificial companions can point out the development crucial of each stage and find the development direction. Perhaps it can even explain whether humans still believe in artificial companions as the

true companions instead of real pets, or whether they have other more important functions. Finally, the study will sum up the future trend of artificial companions and point out the research gaps of artificial companions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The design of artificial companions is originally based on the appearance and behavior of real pets. Therefore, the study is not only to choose the representative artificial companions but also the real pets as the analysis objects to help designers understand the difference of both. The study first summarizes the definition and classification of artificial companions, and then collects relevant literature of artificial companions as the basis of following analysis.

2.1 THE DEFINITION AND CATEGORIES OF ARTIFICIAL COMPANIONS

About the classification of artificial companions, Kriglstein and Wallner (2005) mentioned that the Tamagotchi, Furby, AIBO are classified as artificial companions. Lawson and Chesney (2007a) thought that virtual pets and electronic companions all are artificial companions. Kusahara (2001) mentioned that *even though virtual pets and pet robots are quite different physical entities, they can both be discussed as digital pets*. Benyon and Mival (2008) used the point of view of personification technologies to indicate that the Tamagotchi, Furby, and AIBO all have reached the company function. Based on the above literature, the study finds that the classification and definition of artificial companions is still ambiguous, and there is no study can clear define the scope and classification of artificial companions. In addition, Kusahara (2001) thought that *the basic concept of both virtual pets and pet robots is the offer of entertaining communication with the users, as well as their families and friends*. Kaplan (2001) indicates that *the purpose of an artificial pet is to establish and maintain a relationship with its owner*. In this principle, the study thinks that the scope of artificial companions should include stuffed toys or mechanical toys, which with animal appearance. *After all, children and even some adults form attachments to stuffed animals, dolls, or special "blankies"* (Melson, Kahn, Beck, & Friedman, 2009).

If there are a clear definition and classification of artificial companions; the study can systematic analyze the function and impact of artificial companions to help designers classify the position of each artificial companion and find design guidelines.

2.2 THE RELATED RESEARCH OF THE EVOLUTION OF ARTIFICIAL SCOMPANIONS

According to the existing literature of evolution of artificial companions, there are two studies have clearer instruction (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a; 2007b). However, the two studies just introduced the product information of artificial companions, such as sales, launch time, technology, operational methods, and interactive content. These studies do not discuss about the impact on users and use a systematic method to analyze the artificial companions. In addition, in these two studies, the analysis objects just include Tamagotchi, Petz series, Nintendog, Furby, and AIBO; do not list the real pet, stuffed toys, and mechanical toys into the analysis sample. Furthermore, other studies usually choose a specific topic to do a depth research on one of artificial companions. There is no study analyzing the evolution of artificial companions by a systematic method, so it is difficult to compare the difference of each artificial companion. Moreover, there is no study can clear show the research opportunities, which yet to be explored in the field of artificial companions.

The design concept of artificial companions originally derived from real pets, so this study also collected relevant literature of real pet to have a preliminary understanding the function, impact, and the human-pet relationship. The human needs to be dependent on the animal for purposes that range from economics to healthy effects (Friedmann, Thomas, & Eddy, 2000), but *the attachment between humans and their pets remains relatively undiminished* (Bustad & Hines, 1984; Woodward & Bauer, 2007).

Although most people often use the word: pets, *the term "companion animals" refers primarily to those animals keep for companionship* (Bekoff, 1998). *"Pets" is broader category than "companion animals" and includes animals keep for decorative purpose, those keep for competitive or sporting activities, or keep to satisfy the interests of hobbyists* (Bekoff, 1998).

Odendaal and Lehmann (2000) pointed out that *the human-animal interaction benefits animals as well as people*, for example, physical health benefits (Friedmann, et al., 2000; Odendaal & Lehmann, 2000; Hennessy, Williams, Miller, Douglas, & Voith, 1998), and the psychological effects. Most owners believe that the pet is part of the owner's self (Belk, 1988; Sanders, 1990; Brown, 2004), *such closeness may provide benefits, such as sustaining the owner's core sense of self* (Brown, 2004). Moreover, *raising a real pet can help children develop a humane caring sense of responsibility* (Robin & ten Bensel, 1985) and have a positive impact on children (Pattnaik, 2004).

These studies show that the pets have the positive impact on human and are one of emotional attachment objects for human. However, do the artificial companions have the same function as real pets are worth to be explored.

Therefore, the study also collected relevant literature of artificial companions and found that many studies discuss about the impact of artificial companions. For example, the material and mechanical toys are often to be children's playmates (Campenni, 1999), even these toys cannot interaction with users in two-way but still can reach the healthy and education effect (Plowman & Luckin, 2004; Bratton & Ray, 2000).

Furthermore, there is a study pointed out that the user can get a sense of real accompany from the robotic pets through enough interaction, *children showed positive responses to AIBO during shared reading, and children and adults engaged AIBO as a social partner*. (Melson, et al., 2009). The AIBO also has the positive effect for Alzheimer's patients (Tamura, et al., 2004; Melson, et al., 2009); Kriglstein and Wallner (2005) indicated that an electronic pet is *useful and emphasizes safety, warmth and physical closeness for elders*.

About the virtual pet, Kaplan (2001) thought that Tamagotchi can make users feel responsible; Isbister (2006) mentioned that *virtual pets are relatively unique as autonomous agents since they evoke a high degree of time and emotional investment from the users*; Lawson and Chesney (2007b) indicated that *females do not get more or less companionship from virtual pets than males*. Users may utilize the virtual pet's features to shape their virtual pet as they want and get others' agreement (Wang & Chang, 2009). In

addition, children will learn to play the role of parents when caring for the virtual pet (Li, et al., 2007); virtual pets also may help autistic children understand the real world by playing the online virtual pet game (Altschuler, 2008).

According to the above literature, the function of artificial companions has a great diversity in the development process and different artificial companions truly have different effect on the users. The study thinks that development process and impact of artificial companions should be integrated by a systematic method to clear point out the key points in each stage of artificial companions and find the research opportunities as the design reference.

RESEARCH METHOD

The study chooses the Document Analysis method to sort out the classification of artificial companions and analyze the evolution of artificial companions.

3.1 CHOOSE THE RELATED THEORIES OF ARTIFICIAL COMPANIONS AS ANALYSIS BASIS

This study uses the STS studies, Need-hierarchy theory, and relevant literature to sort out the analysis items of artificial companions. The STS Studies (Science, Technology, and Society Studies) are used to explore the interaction between science, technology, and society. The theory can find out the impact of science and technology on people and society from the past to the present, so it is suitable for analyzing the issue of the artificial companion. The Need-hierarchy theory is used to explain the importance of motivation (Maslow, 1971); this study uses the theory to explore the user's motivation and effect of owning artificial companions. The study also sorts out other materials in relevant literature (such as the appearance of artificial companions), which the Need-hierarchy theory and the STS Studies do not mention, to make the analysis more comprehensive.

3.2 SORT OUT THE ANALYSIS ITEMS OF ARTIFICIAL COMPANIONS

The study chooses related concepts of design from STS Studies, Need-hierarchy theory, and relevant literature as the analysis basis of artificial companions. Finally, the study summarized five categories as the basis for analyzing the evolution of artificial companions. The summarized results of analysis items are in Table 1.

Analysis items	Aspects	
Launch time (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a)	Time	
Price (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a)	Marketing	
User numbers (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a)		
Target groups (Pratt, 1981; Lawson & Chesney, 2007a)		
Use of environment (Piel, 1981)		
Method of disposal (Wallis, 2006)	Space	
Interaction way (Pratt, 1981; Piel, 1981)	Technology	
Game content (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a)		
Main technology (Piel, 1981)		
Appearance (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a)		
Role in user's life (Pratt, 1981)	Function/ Effect	
Health (Pratt, 1981)		
Education (Pratt, 1981; Piel, 1981)		
Peak experience (Maslow, 1971)		
Need-hierarchy theory (Maslow, 1971)		1. Physiological
		2. Safety
	3. Love	
	4. Esteem	
	5. Self-actualization	

Table 1. The analysis items of artificial companions

3.3 CHOOSE THE RELATED DATABASES OF ARTIFICIAL COMPANIONS AS THE LITERATURE RESOURCES

The study selects the electronic databases, which must be contained science, technology, society, and psychology theory, as the literature resources. Then, the study also collects other relevant literature from paper's references to complete the literature collection. This study uses the keywords to search literature. The main keywords include real pet, electronic pet, virtual pet, online pet, pet robot, artificial pet and artificial companion.

The literature is mainly from three databases: (1) ScienceDirect (SDOL, <http://www.sciencedirect.com/>): the database recruits more than 1/4 literature of scientific, technical and medical fields from around the world and with more than 2,000 full-text electronic journals and the bibliographic information; (2) EBSCO Online (<http://ejournals.ebsco.com/>): there are more than 1,200 electronic journals from around the world covering topics that include medicine, computers, mechanical science, biology, economics, finance, marketing management, social sciences, and so on; (3) Index to Taiwan Periodical Literature System (<http://readopac.ncl.edu.tw/nclJournal/>): there are a lot of papers are published in Chinese and Western journals after 1970 in Taiwan and about 4,800 journals and periodicals published in the Hong Kong and Macao areas.

3.4 USE THE LITERATURE DOCUMENTS TO SORT OUT THE CLASSIFICATION OF ARTIFICIAL COMPANIONS

After the literature collection, the study finds that the classification of artificial companions is unclear in the existing literature, and this will affect the analysis objectivity of artificial companions. Therefore, the study tries to integrate the classification of artificial companions before the evolution analysis. This study chooses the "real pet" as the initial analysis object and then base on the developmental sequence to analyze all types of artificial companions.

The study thinks that the scope of artificial companions in addition to include the pet robots and virtual pets but include the stuffed toys, mechanical and electronic toys with animal appearances. These toys also own the features of artificial companions and they are the normal types, which most users often get in touch with.

This study relies on the relevant literature (Kusahara, 2001; Kaplan, 2001; Kriglstein & Wallner, 2005; Lawson & Chesney, 2007a; Benyon & Mival, 2008; Bekoff, 1998) and the existing artificial companions in the market to summarize the classification of artificial companions. Finally, the study draws the classification diagram of artificial companions as Figure1; this classification is only for the pet-type of artificial companions.

Figure 1. Classification of artificial companions as pets

3.5 DRAW AN ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK, AND PUT THE RELEVANT LITERATURE INTO THE ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK

After drawing the classification of artificial companions, the study bases on the launch time of artificial companions as the analysis sequence, then picks up the representative artificial companions as

the analysis samples. Finally, the study sets an analysis framework as Table 2.

According to the literature collection results, the study chooses the relevant contents to fill in the Table 2. If there are columns cannot be filled in any literature, the study uses another font to mark the insufficient research of artificial companions.

Analysis items		Step1: Fill in analysis items (Table1)	
Pet types			
Real pet	Step2: According to time sequence		
Artifica1 companion1			
Artifica1 companion2			Step3: Fill in the relevant literature contents
...			
Artifica1 companion n			

Table2. The analysis framework of artificial companions

3.6 PICK UP KEY WORDS IN ANAYSIS FRANEWORK, THEN SORT OUT THE ANALYSIS RESULTS

In accordance with the previous results, the study uses the keywords to mark the key factors of the

evolution of artificial companions (as Table 3). Next, the study simplifies the analysis results to summarize each phase of artificial companions and names for all phases as the final results. The study also integrates the insufficient parts from the analysis results as a reference for academia.

Analysis items		All analysis items (as Table1)
Pet types		
Real pet		Pick up the important factors of the evolution of artificial companions by keywords.
Artifica1 companion1		
Artifica1 companion2		
...		
Artifica1 companion n		

Table3. Key points of the evolution of artificial companions

RESULTS

The study bases on the research method to get the initial analysis results (Table 4) and the bold italic font in Table 4 means the insufficient literature in artificial companions.

Analysis items		Launch time	Marketing			Space	
			Price	User numbers	Target groups	Use of environment	Method of disposal
Real pet		12,000 years ago (Bekoff, 1998)	Determined by species	2010 in U.S. 72,000,000	Anyone, in addition to children needs adults' assistance.	Pet can be carried at most locations. However, some cities, due to limited space, do not allow the keeping of pets (Kano, 2008).	Thrown away, given away, or placed in animal shelters.
Artificial companions	Mechanical	16th century	>5 USD.	In general case, a child at least has one.	Most boys (Campenni, 1999)	Home, or can be carried out.	The disposal method is the same as that of general toys (gift, garbage, etc.).
	Material	1880 (Cross, 1999)	>35 USD. (Teddy bear)		Most girls (Campenni, 1999)		
	Single-machine Virtual pet (Tamagotchi)	1996	15/pounds	50,000,000	Students and young people (Kusahara, 2001).		
	Entity electronic pet (Furby, AIBO)	1998	Furby: 50 USD. AIBO: 1400/pounds	Furby: 40,000,000 AIBO<200,000	Adults and young people (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a).		
	Online pet (Neopet)	1999	Free	180,000,000	10-18 years old group (Yang, 2006).		
	Single-machine Virtual pet (Nintendog)	2005	30 pounds	7,000,000	Young or adult female (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a).		
	Blog pet (Meromero)	2005	Free	70,000	Mostly women (Wu, 2008)		
Virtual pet game in social game	2007	Free	>45,000,000	No study.	Any devices with a web function, such as computers or portable electronic products.	Virtual pets can reduce the problem of abandonment of real pets, but the online virtual pets also have the problem of being abandoned as well (Wallis, 2006).	

Table4. The detail analysis process of the evolution of artificial companions (continued)

Analysis items		Space	Technology	
Pet types		Interaction way	Game content	Main Technology
Real pet		<i>Various factors have been offered to explain the strength of human-animal attachment—including lifestyle dictates (Arkow & Dow, 1984) and individual differences accounted for by the pet owner (Brown & Katcher, 2001; Woodward & Bauer, 2007).</i>	/	
Artificial companions	Mechanical	In the physical plane, the user utilizes the imagination to interact with the toy. <i>Interaction methods including action and gesture, expression and gaze, and dialogue.</i> (Plowman & Luckin, 2004).	Showing the repetitive movements, the user changes the actions of the toy is according to mechanical power.	Mechanical toys are powered by mechanical energy, such as by using rubber bands, springs, or flywheels.
	Material		The user plays with the toy through personal imagination, such as speaking or role playing, but the toys cannot have any real response.	A toy sewn from cloth, plush, or other textiles and stuffed with plastic pellets, cotton, synthetic fibers, or other similar materials (Cross, 1999).
	Single-machine Virtual pet (Tamagotchi)	<i>Users could feed, clean and play with their Tamagotchi, call it via the microphone and chase away predators by shaking the unit</i> (Bloch & Lemish, 1999).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to feed, clean, and play with the pet. • The user calls the pet via the microphone and chase away predators by shaking the unit. • The pet would die or fly away over time. (Bloch & Lemish, 1999).	<i>About the size of a key ring, a typical Tamagotchi had a small black and white screen, three buttons, a speaker, a motion sensor and a microphone</i> (Lawson & Chesney, 2007c).
	Entity electronic pet (Furby, AIBO)	In the physical plane, robots can be used for various games, as well as serve as a pet. <i>When people enjoy it as a pet, a possible configuration may be a legged robot with a head</i> (Fujita, et al., 1999).	<i>Autonomous robots present a new possibility; they resemble living creatures both in their appearance and self-propelled motion with high degree of freedom.</i> (Kubinyi, 2004).	<i>AIBO senses the situation and surroundings of its environment by a camera built-in, microphones and sensors. AIBO with a Memory Stick™ is able to learn, to express its needs and six emotions, via light-emitting diodes in the eyes and in the tail, body language and using sounds</i> (Kubinyi, 2004).
	Online pet (Neopet)	User interacts with the pet, the virtual scene, as well as other pets through the Internet (Yang, 2006; Victor, 2008).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to feed, clean, dress up, and play with pet. • Game content updates regularly. • Pet plays with other pets through the Internet. (Yang, 2006).	The game can retain the accumulated data, objects, and scenes from the last time by the Internet, and these variations of action can be stored in the game (Lee, 1998). These games are established by Flash Player, Shockwave, or 3D Life Player.
	Single-machine Virtual pet (Nintendog)	<i>Users can actually touch their screen based pet through the touch screen and exploit the wireless network capability allow Nintendogs to play with each other</i> (Lawson & Chesney, 2008).	<i>Nintendog shows owners' virtual, animated puppy, (their Nintendog) which they must feed, water, walk, play with and train. User's Nintendog can play with others' pets though the wireless network</i> (Lawson & Chesney, 2007c).	<i>Users run the Nintendog software on the handheld games-console, the Nintendo DS, which features two full color screens, one of which is touch sensitive.</i> (Lawson & Chesney, 2007c).
	Blog pet (Meromero)	User updates the blog frequently and the blog pet will learn the article texts The pet also can visit other's blog pets via the Internet (Wu, 2008).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to feed, clean, dress up, and play with pet. • User can decorate pet's home. • The number of blog articles decides the pet is growth rate. • User can visit friends' pets to increase interaction. (Wu, 2008).	The game can retain the accumulated data, objects, and scenes from the last time by the Internet, and these variations of action can be stored in the game (Lee, 1998). These games are established by Flash Player, Shockwave, or 3D Life Player.
	Virtual pet game in social game	User joins in game activities, interacts with the pet and the virtual scene through social networks, and can also play with friends' pets through the links of the social networks (Pet Society, 2011).	(1)Need to feed, clean, dress up and play with pet; (2) game content updates regularly; (3) user can decorate pet's home for free; (4) user needs to join a variety of game activities to earn virtual money and virtual goods; playing with friends' pets can increase interaction and the game level (Pet Society, 2011).	

Analysis items		Technology	Function / Effect			
Pet types	Appearance	Role in user's life	Health	Education		
Real pet	Real	<i>Pet can assist the disabled, herd livestock, provide security, find identity markers of being a pet-lover, choose specific breeds as symbols of status, fill roles of avocation, ornament, and toy</i> (Cavanaugh, et al., 2008). Most pet owners treat their pet like a family member, friend, and even as a child (Mosteller, 2008; Askew, 1996).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raising pets can lower blood pressure, reduce stress, prevent heart disease, and fight depression and loneliness (A.P.P.A., 2008). Pets may help to nurture and sustain people through stressful situations (Allen Blascovich, & Mendes, 2002), with women and children experiencing particular benefits (Allen, et al., 2002; Strand, 2004) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How adults treat pets may influence how their children respond to pets as adults (Raupp, 1999). Pet's presence in childhood may influence one's degree of attachment toward pets in adulthood (Kidd and Kidd, 1989). Raising a pet helps children develop a humane caring sense of responsibility (Robin & ten Bensel, 1985). 		
	Mechanical	Mimics real pet or has a personified appearance	<i>Toys should be safe, affordable, and developmentally appropriate. Toys should be appealing to engage the child over a period of time</i> (Glassy & Romano, 2003).	Positive effects of play therapy: social maladjustment, conduct disorder or aggression, emotional maladjustment, self-concept, intelligence, reading, physical or learning disability, speech or language problems, etc (Bratton & Ray, 2000).	Playing with dolls, trucks, blocks, and similar toys encourages children to be the "creators and controllers of their play" (Plowman & Luckin, 2004).	
Artificial companions	Material	Mimics real pets	Raising the Tamagotchi can make users feel responsible (Kaplan, 2001). However, there is no other study discussing about the role of virtual pets in the user's life.	No study.		
	Single-machine Virtual pet (Tamagotchi)	Mimics real pets	Raising the Tamagotchi can make users feel responsible (Kaplan, 2001). However, there is no other educational research on the virtual pet.	Raising the Tamagotchi can make users feel responsible (Kaplan, 2001). However, there is no other educational research on the virtual pet.		
	Entity electronic pet (Furby, AIBO)	<i>Be made to look like a real puppy and would act like a real puppy</i> (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a).	Children and adults see the entity electronic pet as a real pet, a family member, or a friend, and the user can get a sense of real companionship from the pet (Melson, et al., 2009).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elderly with severe dementia increased their activity and social behavior with AIBO as compared to a stuffed animal (Tamura, et al., 2004; Melson, et al., 2009). It is useful and emphasizes safety, warmth and physical closeness for elders (Kriglstein & Wallner, 2005). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Furby is aimed directly at children is the talking 'educational' toy (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a). Children showed positive responses to AIBO during shared reading (Decuir, Kozuki, Matsuda, & Piazza, 2004; Melson, et al., 2009). 	
	Online pet (Neopet)	Abstractive appearance of creature, about 50 types (Yang, 2006).	Isbister (2006) <i>attempts to rationalize peoples' motivations for engaging with a virtual pet is to enjoy the pet's development as well as its moments of both connection and resistance to the user.</i> In this way Isbister (2006) <i>identifies that virtual pets are relatively unique as autonomous agents in games since they evoke a high degree of time and emotional investment from the users.</i> However, what the role of virtual pets plays in the user's life still needs to be studied.	Relieves stress to achieve the function of regulating life (Huang, 2002; Wood, Giles corti, & Bulsara, 2005; Li, Tseng, & Huang, 2007). But there is no other study about health effects.	Children will learn to play the role of parents when caring for the virtual pet (Li, et al., 2007). However, there is no other educational research on the virtual pet.	
	Single-machine Virtual pet (Nintendog)	Mimics real pets	Isbister (2006) <i>attempts to rationalize peoples' motivations for engaging with a virtual pet is to enjoy the pet's development as well as its moments of both connection and resistance to the user.</i> In this way Isbister (2006) <i>identifies that virtual pets are relatively unique as autonomous agents in games since they evoke a high degree of time and emotional investment from the users.</i> However, what the role of virtual pets plays in the user's life still needs to be studied.	No study.		
	Blog pet (Meromero)	Personified appearance by personal settings	Isbister (2006) <i>attempts to rationalize peoples' motivations for engaging with a virtual pet is to enjoy the pet's development as well as its moments of both connection and resistance to the user.</i> In this way Isbister (2006) <i>identifies that virtual pets are relatively unique as autonomous agents in games since they evoke a high degree of time and emotional investment from the users.</i> However, what the role of virtual pets plays in the user's life still needs to be studied.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relieves stress to achieve the function of regulating life (Huang, 2002; Li, Tseng, & Huang, 2007) Altschuler (2008) indicates that it may help autistic children understand the real world play the online virtual pet game. But there is no other study about health effects.		
	Virtual pet game in social game	Personified appearance by personal settings	Isbister (2006) <i>attempts to rationalize peoples' motivations for engaging with a virtual pet is to enjoy the pet's development as well as its moments of both connection and resistance to the user.</i> In this way Isbister (2006) <i>identifies that virtual pets are relatively unique as autonomous agents in games since they evoke a high degree of time and emotional investment from the users.</i> However, what the role of virtual pets plays in the user's life still needs to be studied.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relieves stress to achieve the function of regulating life (Huang, 2002; Li, Tseng, & Huang, 2007) Altschuler (2008) indicates that it may help autistic children understand the real world play the online virtual pet game. But there is no other study about health effects.		

Analysis items		Function / Effect					
		Peak experience	Need-hierarchy theory				
Pet types	Physiological		Safety	Love	Esteem	Self-actualization	
Real pet		No study	People do not need to fulfill physical needs with the pet.	Pets have a security function (Cavanaugh, et al., 2008).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A pet may provide physical and emotional support during a person's significant life events (Mosteller, 2008). • People may talk to pets, treating them as surrogate humans (Sanders, 1990). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pet sustains the owner's core sense of self (Brown, 2004) • Some owners choose specific breeds as symbols of status (Sanders, 1990; Hirschman, 1994). 	<i>Pets bring relaxation, comforts, and peace of mind to enhance the happiness of humans</i> (Holbrook & Woodside, 2008).
Artificial companions	Mechanical	When a user interacts with an artificial companion they may have the peak experience. Although there are many studies discussing in immersion and addiction for online games, in the field of artificial companions there is no study related to immersion and addiction.		Provides children with a sense of security.	Toys can provide a bridge for a child's interactions with parents or other caregivers. (Glassy & Romano, 2003).	A child's self-esteem and level of mastery are also enhanced when adults participate in play (Glassy & Romano, 2003).	No study.
	Material						
	Single-machine Virtual pet (Tamagotchi)			No provision.	Virtual pets have a social function, but what social benefits and social depths can be achieved so far have no study to explain them.	No study.	
	Entity electronic pet (Furby, AIBO)			It is useful and emphasizes safety, warmth, (Kriglstein & Wallner, 2005).	Children and adults think of the AIBO as a social partner in some way (Yokoyama, et al., 2004; Kerepesi, Kubinyi, Jonsson, Magnusson, & Miklosi, 2006; Pepe, Ellis, Sims, & Chin, 2008; Melson, et al., 2009).		
	Online pet (Neopet)			No provision.	Virtual pets have a social function, but what social benefits and social depths can be achieved so far have no study to explain them.		
	Single-machine Virtual pet (Nintendo)				Users have the emotional attachment with the virtual pet and females and males the same companionship from virtual pets (Lawson & Chesney, 2007b). What social benefits and social depths can be achieved so far have no study to explain them.		
	Blog pet (Meromero)					To raise a virtual pet can make the user interact with others to meet the social needs (Wang & Chang, 2009). What social benefits and social depths can be achieved so far have no study to explain them.	
Virtual pet game in social game							

Table4. The detail analysis process of the evolution of artificial companions

According to the Table 4, the study selects some important factors of the evolution of artificial companions through keywords method, simplifies the analysis results, and concludes the key points of all evolution phases of artificial companions (Table 5), the evolution process of artificial companions is divided into 5 phases (the right column of Table 5).

Analysis items	Launch Time	Marketing		Space		Technology		Function / Effect					Evolution induction	Real interaction	Imagination-driving	Mimicry of reality	Multiple activity	Intellectual interaction																
		Price	User numbers	Target groups	Use of environment	Method of disposal	Interaction way	Appearance	Game content	Main technology	Role in user's life	Healthy							Education	Peak experience	Need-hierarchy theory	Self-actualization	Esteem	Love	Safety	Physiological								
Pet types	12,000 years ago	Real money	Increases gradually	All	Physical space	Multi-directional interaction	Real	/	Multiple relationships	Benefits of Physiology and psychology.	Raising a pet helps children develop a humane caring sense of responsibility.	No study.	Not need to provide.	Security function	Emotional attachment	Self-awareness	Bring peace of mind to enhance the happiness.	No study.	Enhance children's self-esteem.	Children interact with parent or caregivers.	Children's sense of security	Not need to provide.	No provision.	Two-way social interaction	Safety reminder	Multi-dimensional social interaction.	No provision.	No study.	Physical closeness for elders	Multiple relationships	No study.	Relieves stress	Virtual community	
		Real money		Gradually be placed by electron or digital toys.	Children		Physical space																											One-way interaction
Artificial companions	Mechanical	16 th century	Gradually be placed by electron or digital toys.	Children	Physical space	One-way interaction	Mimic reality	Speaking or role playing	Non-digital	Playmate, learning tools	Help children's psychological development	Encourages children to be the creators and controllers.	No study.	Not need to provide.	Children's sense of security	Enhance children's self-esteem.	Children interact with parent or caregivers.	Children's sense of security	Not need to provide.	No provision.	Two-way social interaction	Safety reminder	Multi-dimensional social interaction.	No provision.	No study.	Physical closeness for elders	Multiple relationships	No study.	Relieves stress	Virtual community				
	Material (Teddy bear)	1880																													More than entity electronic pets	Children, young, adult	Virtual space	Two-way interaction
	Single-machine virtual pet (Tamagotchi)	1996	Increases gradually	Children, young, adult	Physical space	Two-way interaction	Mimic reality	Speaking or role playing	Non-digital	Playmate, learning tools	Help children's psychological development	Encourages children to be the creators and controllers.	No study.	Not need to provide.	Children's sense of security	Enhance children's self-esteem.	Children interact with parent or caregivers.	Children's sense of security	Not need to provide.	No provision.	Two-way social interaction	Safety reminder	Multi-dimensional social interaction.	No provision.	No study.	Physical closeness for elders	Multiple relationships	No study.	Relieves stress	Virtual community				
	Entity electronic pet (Furby, AIBO)	1998																													More than entity electronic pets	Children, young, adult	Physical space	Two-way interaction
	Online pet (Neopet)	1999	Virtual Currency	More than entity electronic pets.	Young, adult	Virtual space	Multi-directional interaction	Abstractive appearance	Multiple activities (Raising, play, and social)	With network	Spiritual comfort for autistic children	No study.	No study.	Not need to provide.	No provision.	Multi-dimensional social interaction.	No provision.	No study.	Virtual abandonment, no responsibility.	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency
	Single-machine virtual pet (Nintendog)	2005	Real money																															
	Blog pet (Meromero)	2005	Virtual Currency	More than entity electronic pets.	Female	Virtual space	Multi-directional interaction	Abstractive appearance	Multiple activities (Raising, play, and social)	With network	Spiritual comfort for autistic children	No study.	No study.	Not need to provide.	No provision.	Multi-dimensional social interaction.	No provision.	No study.	Virtual abandonment, no responsibility.	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency	Virtual Currency
	Virtual pet game in social game (Pet society)	2007	Virtual Currency																															

Table5. The key factors and five phases of the evolution of artificial companions

(1) Real interaction: until the 16th century, before the artificial companions appeared, the needs of emotional attachment were met for human by keeping the real pets. Until now, real pets still play an important companionship role in human life. (2) Imagination-driving: there were stuffed toys, mechanical toys, and other non-electronic artificial pets from the 16th to 20th centuries, and human beings took those artificial pets as life playmates. The interaction is one-way. (3) Mimicry of reality: the first independent virtual pet device called Tamagotchi launched in 1996. The virtual pets took the world by storm because it was easy to feed and would become sick and die just like real pets; later on, some entity electronic pets with similar real responses and features were introduced. At this time, the artificial companion was expected to achieve the companionship function of real pets. (4) Multiple activity: after 1999, the Internet spread worldwide and it made online virtual pets popular. The process of raising virtual pets is emphasized and interest is perked through multiple game activities. These activities make users feel enjoyment by taking care of a virtual pet. (5) Intellectual interaction: due to the launch of cloud technology and social networks since 2007, the virtual pets have become more intelligent and have their own personalities. It can not only show the personal characteristics of the users but also allow users to have social interactions or share their life with friends through virtual pet games.

From the "User numbers" of Table 4, the study found that tens of millions of artificial companion users in the world enjoy interacting with, playing with and investing time in these artificial companions and as there have many industries invested money in this market (Lawson & Chesney, 2007a). However, there are few researches discussing on virtual pets, the study sorts out some research issues, which rare be discussed on artificial companions from the bold italic font in Table 4 as a reference (Table 6).

The academia should concern about the impact of artificial companions, especially the online virtual pet, which has a large number of users. There is no study discussing the cognition of users to the virtual pet, the differences between virtual pets and real pets, the design factors of virtual pets which can cause emotional attachments, or whether the virtual pets have the healthy effect, education value. Do

virtual pets can help the user to achieve states of immersion, addiction, or peak experience? There have not clear answers.

Analysis items		Lack studies regarding the artificial companion
Marketing	Target groups	No study clearly points out the target group of the virtual pet in social games.
	Role in user's life	Although users have emotional attachments with online virtual pets, but there is no study that can prove the role of the virtual pet in the user's life.
Function / Effect	Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single-machine Virtual pet: No study. • Entity electronic pets have the function of psychotherapy for the elderly, but no other relevant studies. • Online pet: No study. • Virtual pet in social game: Helps relieve stress, but no other relevant studies.
	Education	Virtual pet in social game: No study.
	Peak experience	Artificial companion: It is possible to have the peak experience when the user interacts with the artificial companion, but there is no study that can prove it.
	Need-hierarchy theory	
Need-hierarchy theory	Love	The virtual pet can make a user interact with other users but there is no study that can explain the social benefits clearly.
	Esteem	Digital pet: No study.
	Self-actualization	Artificial companion: No study.

Table6. The research opportunities of artificial companions

The study also infers the future trend of artificial companions from the above results (Table 4 & 5). The study thinks that the trend of artificial companions will follow the multi-machines virtual pet and proceed to the "user-image projection" stage: the virtual pet will have a personified appearance, autonomic features, and be represented as user themselves to express the user's thoughts. Moreover, the social network in virtual pet game can reflect the users' social relationships in the real life. The virtual pet will have autonomy and flexibility to adapt to the physical and social environment, with part of the features of the real pet and a personified appearance. The virtual pet can also make users have a wide interaction with other users.

CONCLUSION

Mival, Cringean, and Benyon (2004) discussed the *design of artificial companions suggest that the inherent characteristics of a companion transform an interaction into a relationship and evoke an emotional investment.* In the future, designers will develop better artificial companions to make the user have a

deeper emotional attachment. However, the study finds that while the artificial companion emphasizes the feeding function at first now it also allows the user to create a personal style of artificial companion and users can interact with other users via their artificial companion; this means that the function of the artificial companion has changed dramatically.

Now, it is not sure whether or not the artificial companion is still considered as an alternative of the real pet and there are many different relationships between users and artificial companions, such as that of the owner and pet, friendship, parent-child, or even some personal-image projection by the user on the artificial companion. The artificial companion may represent users themselves in the future and the user will establish a new friendship or social relationships through the artificial companion.

From the analysis result of the evolution of the artificial companion the study infers that the users of virtual pets are more popular than other artificial companions, and this suggests that the main marketing of artificial companions will be the virtual pet. However, this study also finds that there are rare researches discussing on the companionship and interaction with virtual pet. If we can answer these questions, these research results will help designer to develop better products or games. Therefore, the study will choose the multi-machines virtual pet as the future research object and try to figure out the virtual pet's position, role characteristics, social implications, and design factors as the design recommendations in the next evolutionary stage.

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